

Modeling of Melodic Rhythm Based on Entropy toward Creating Expectation and Emotion

Hidefumi Ohmura

JST, ERATO, Okanoya Emotional Information Project, Japan, and Riken, Saitama, Japan
ohmura@brain.riken.jp

Takuro Shibayama

Tokyo Denki University, Saitama, Japan
takuro@mail.dendai.ac.jp

Satoshi Shibuya

Tokyo Denki University, Saitama, Japan
shibuya@rd.dendai.ac.jp

Tatsuji Takahashi

Tokyo Denki University, Saitama, Japan
tatsuji@mail.dendai.ac.jp

Kazuo Okanoya

JST, ERATO, Okanoya Emotional Information Project, Japan, Riken, Saitama, Japan, and The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan
kazuookanoya@gmail.com

Kiyoshi Furukawa

Tokyo University of the Arts, Tokyo, Japan
furukawa@zkm.de

ABSTRACT

The act of listening to music can be regarded as a sequence of expectations about the nature of the next segment in the musical piece. While listening to music, the listener infers how the next section of a musical piece would sound based on whether or not the previous inferences were confirmed. However, if the listener's expectations continue to be satisfied, the listener will gradually want a change in the music. Therefore, the pleasant betrayal of the listener's expectations is important to evoke emotion in music. The increase and decrease of local complexities in the music structure are deeply involved in the betrayal of expectation. Nevertheless, no quantitative research has been conducted in this area of study. We already validated that entropy in sets of note pitches are closely related to the listeners' feeling of complexity. Therefore, in this paper, we propose a model that is able to generate a melodic rhythm based on entropy in sets of note values, and then we validate the suitability of the model in terms of complexities of rhythm through a psychological experiment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Meyer pointed out that the deviations of expectations arouse emotions when listening to music [1], based on Dewey's theory that conflict causes emotions [2]. Narmour defined the relation between expectation and deviation/realization as the IR (implication-realization) theory [3]. Huron also proposed the ITPRA Theory of Expectation [4]. These research studies indicate that the deviation/realization of expectations could have an influence on musically induced emotions. In these theories, the generation and deviation/realization of expectation are defined as rules based on intuitive feelings; therefore, the theories are difficult to implement directly on computers.

Therefore, we propose a model to calculate the deviation/realization of expectation to be able to generate music automatically within a perspective. Deviation from the expectation of the listener when listening to music is brought by the partial or complete disregard of rules that were accepted in advance. This indicates an increase of entropy from the viewpoint of informatics theory because of its augmented uncertainties. These uncertainties have a commonality with the complexity in the optimal-complexity model [5], which illustrates the relation between complexity and pleasure. This commonality suggests the existence of a relation between uncertainty and emotion. Therefore, uncertainty could be calculated, based on the order of the musical sequence generated using entropy. The important characteristic of this research is the viewpoint that controlling entropy in melodies elicits emotions.

Generally, melodies can be described as sets of pitches and values of musical notes. Timbre is also one of the elements that indicate the characteristics of melodies; however, we used a melody-generation system that considers only the pitches of musical notes. In this paper, the model about the uncertainty of rhythm was the basis for the generation of rhythm in our melodies, while we focused our attention to the duration of musical notes that form the melody. Then we developed the system of melody generation and verified the appropriateness of this model by experiment.

2. MUSICAL CONSTRUCTION AND COMPLEXITY

2.1 Musical Construction for Musical Expectation

Based on Meyer's theory that emotion arises when the music deviates from the listener's expectations, Narmour proposed the IR theory, which treats the listener's expectation as an "implication." Two sequential notes have a specific relation, which creates an expectation or "implication" of the next note. The third musical note brings the "realization" for the "implication." If the listener incor-

rectly guessed the third musical note, then the music evokes emotion. We attempted to generate melodies by developing a system that produces the various pitch transition possibilities of two sequential notes with symmetry biases, which is a human illogical reasoning process brought on by human intuition [6]. As a result, this system, which is the core of this research, was able to generate melodies that can offer the listener musical coordination or musical unpredictability. Through these analyses of melodies, we find that the feelings of *unity* and *unpredictability* are closely related to entropy in expressing musical complexities, a similar close relationship could exist between melodic rhythm and entropy.

2.2 Entropy

The theories for musical deviation/realization of expectations are not appropriate for computer system implementations, because they are based on intuition and are not quantitative but qualitative. We propose a computation model of complexity to create musical deviation/realization of expectations so that we can develop an automatic system to create music that can evoke musical emotion. To substantiate the model of musical complexity, we use information theory [1], which provides the quantity of information to be delivered. Music elicits a listener's emotion with temporal structures of musical notes. By modeling the structures based on information theory, we can create music that can evoke emotions.

In information theory, when event i occurs, the amounts of information are defined as

$$I = -\log p_i \quad (1)$$

where p_i is the probability of event i . When n events occur with the probabilities p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n , the expected values are calculated as

$$H = -\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log p_i \quad (2)$$

The value H represents the amount of information to be delivered, i.e., the degree of uncertainty and complexity.

3. PROPOSED MODEL

3.1 Creation of Melodic Rhythm

Melody is characterized by many factors, such as note value (duration of a note), pitch (frequency), and timbre (tone color). We developed a system that automatically creates complex melodies using the relationships among the pitches of notes. The entropy of the transitions between pitches creates the human cognition of complexity.

In this paper, we propose a model of complexity by adjusting the note value. The minimum rhythmic pattern is pulse-framed by a repeated arbitrary time interval, which is called a metrical structure. A pulse becomes a complex

Figure 1. How to divide metrical structure

rhythm by extending or shortening the note value. To create rhythm, notes are positioned on a metrical structure, and their positions divide the metrical structures. Repeated divisions by a prime number can create various positions in a metrical structure. The typical number of division used in music is two or three. Five or higher divisions are infrequently used, probably because humans have difficulty perceiving such rhythms. For example, a quintuplet note or five beats are understood to be $2 + 3$, and a septuplet note or seven beats are understood to be $2 + 2 + 3$. Moreover, a rhythm with a mixed number of divisions is more difficult to perceive [8]. They suggest divisions by two or three to create melodic rhythm patterns. In this study, we only consider a division by two for the sake of simplicity.

Figure 1 shows the division of a metrical structure and the note positions at each level. Lv.1 includes a position created, but not a division. Lv.2 includes a position created in a division by one. Similarly, the levels Lv.3, Lv.4, Lv.5, and Lv.6 include positions created in divisions by two, three, four, and five, respectively. At four-quarter time, a whole note is set at a position as in Lv.1, and thirty-second notes are set at positions as in Lv.6. Although divisions greater than Lv.6 exist, they are not necessarily elements of a melodic rhythm, because sixty-four and shorter notes may not be perceived by the listener. Therefore, we use positions of notes from Lv.1 to Lv.6 only. In this research, a metrical structure consists of 32 positions, and the melodic rhythm is created by selecting these 32 positions.

3.2 Creation of Entropy

Entropy is calculated from the probabilities of selecting a position out of 32 positions. From Lv.1 to Lv.6, each position has a weight. A lower position has a greater weight than higher positions. The reason is that listeners may have difficulty perceiving notes at a higher position, because dividing a position creates new positions in the next higher level.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

Table 1. weights and probability ($\sigma = 10$)

	Lv. 1	Lv. 2	Lv. 3	Lv. 4	Lv. 5	Lv. 6
x	0	12	24	36	48	60
w	9978	4855	560	16	1	1
p	0.647	0.315	0.036	0.001	0.000	0.000

Figure 2. The application system with the model

This equation describes the normal distribution with the mean μ and variance σ^2 . The division at each level is substituted for x in the equation. μ is 0. By controlling σ , we can obtain values such as the weights of each position. We calculate the magnitude of the weights as

$$w = f(x) \times 2.5 \times 10^5 \quad (4)$$

For example, when $\sigma = 10$ and each x is set as indicated in Table 1, we obtain the weight w and the probability p as shown in Table 1 using (3) and (4). By entering these probabilities in (2), we get entropy $H = 1.115$. Melodic rhythms are created by probabilities, and our experimental melodies are introduced in 4.3.

3.3 Implementation of Model

We implemented the model in a system written in Java. The system can be downloaded from "http://emotion.brain.riken.jp/music/app/CMM.jar." It has an interface consisting of four panels, as shown in Figure 2.

The Main Panel, which is located at the top-left corner, has a melody generation button, a play melody button, a selector of identical metrical iteration counts, a check box for automatic continuous creation of metrical structures, a selector of the sample size, a selector of the limitation in the number of notes in a metrical structure, a selector of the number of pitches, a selector of the tempo, and the SMF output button.

The Control Panel, which is located at the top-right corner, has selectors of weights for each level and a selector of the variance σ . Although each selector of weight is

Figure 3. Three Gaussian curves for melodies

Table 2. Experimental parameter

σ	p						H
	Lv.1	Lv.2	Lv.3	Lv.4	Lv.5	Lv.6	
10	0.647	0.315	0.036	0.001	0.000	0.000	1.115
20	0.389	0.323	0.188	0.076	0.022	0.004	1.947
50	0.210	0.204	0.188	0.163	0.133	0.102	2.544

independent, all weights are decided by selecting the variance.

The Score Panel, which is located at the bottom-left corner, shows a melody being created as a 32x32 sequencer whose x-axis indicates time and whose y-axis indicates the pitch.

The Movement Panel, which is located at the bottom-right corner, shows the movement of pitch as a red ball in circle of fifths. A big circle means higher pitch, and a small circle means lower pitch.

The Device Selection Panel, which is hidden, allows the selection of MIDI devices.

4. EXPERIMENT

4.1 Experimental Purpose and Participants

The purpose of the experiment is to confirm that the listener can distinguish differences between melodies based on different entropies.

Out of 25 participants, five did not understand the purpose of the experiment: two participants assigned the same points to all melodies, and three participants compared the melodies with popular music. Therefore, we analyzed the data of only 20 participants (men: 11, women: 9; mean age: 31.57, SD: 9.11).

4.2 Experimental System

The experiment was conducted on a Webpage written in PHP and JavaScript. Each participant accessed the site with arbitrary computers. After listening to the melodies with players on the experimental Webpage, they ap-

Figure 4. Sample of melodies

praised the melodies by assigning appraisal labels. They were instructed to listen in a quiet environment or with an earphone or a headphone and to adjust the volume to a comfortable level.

4.3 Experimental Melody

We created melodies under three conditions ($\sigma = 10, 20, 50$), whose settings in a Gaussian curve are shown in Figure 3. Table 2 shows the probabilities and entropies of those three conditions. Melodies created from these three conditions were called Melody 1, Melody 2, and Melody 3. All melodies lasted for one minute and consisted of eight bars. Each bar in each melody had six notes. We generated at least 75 melodies, so that each participant listened to three unique melodies. Figure 4 shows a sample of the melodies at each level. The melodies were played for the participants in a random order to avoid order effects.

4.4 Appraisal Label

Participants were provided the following appraisal labels to identify their sensory perception of the melodies. The words in parentheses are abbreviations, which we used as appellative appraisal labels. Participants appraised the melodies on a five-point scale, where 1 is the lowest appraisal meaning they feel nothing, and 5 is the highest appraisal meaning they feel something strongly.

- You feel the rhythm. (*Rhythm*)
- You feel a musical unity. (*Unity*)
- You feel a complexity. (*Complexity*)
- You feel amusement. (*Amusement*)
- You feel positive emotion. (*Positive*)
- You feel negative emotion. (*Negative*)
- You like it. (*Like*)

The orders of the appraised labels were randomized for each participant to avoid order effects.

Table 3. Means and result of ANOVA * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Melody		1 ($H = 1.115$)	2 ($H = 1.947$)	3 ($H = 2.544$)
<i>Rhythm</i>	Mean (SD)	3.4 (0.995)	3.15 (1.137)	2.25 (1.020)
	ANOVA	$F(2, 57) = 6.609, p = 0.003^{**}$		
<i>Unity</i>	Mean (SD)	2.85 (0.988)	2.55 (0.999)	2.05 (0.945)
	ANOVA	$F(2, 57) = 3.420, p = 0.040^*$		
<i>Complexity</i>	Mean (SD)	2.85 (1.127)	2.65 (1.182)	3.55 (1.050)
	ANOVA	$F(2, 57) = 3.262, p = 0.046^*$		
<i>Amusement</i>	Mean (SD)	2.8 (1.005)	2.75 (0.786)	2.85 (1.226)
	ANOVA	$F(2, 57) = 0.479, p = 0.953$		
<i>Positive</i>	Mean (SD)	2.45 (1.146)	2.45 (0.887)	2.55 (1.356)
	ANOVA	$F(2, 57) = 0.508, p = 0.951$		
<i>Negative</i>	Mean (SD)	2.2 (1.005)	2.1 (1.071)	2.45 (1.099)
	ANOVA	$F(2, 57) = 0.579, p = 0.564$		
<i>Like</i>	Mean (SD)	2.2 (0.952)	2.6 (1.273)	2.4 (1.429)
	ANOVA	$F(2, 57) = 0.525, p = 0.594$		

4.5 Experimental Procedure

The experiment was conducted using the following procedure:

1. Accessing the experimental Webpage with arbitrary computers.
2. Reading the experimental manual, and answering questions such as age and gender.
3. Listening to melodies, and appraising them.
4. Completing the appraisal of the melodies and sending the appraisal data.

4.6 Experimental Result

We analyzed the appraisal data for each appraisal label using ANOVA. Table 3 shows the results.

Rhythm, *Unity*, and *Complexity* showed significant differences among the melodies; therefore, we analyzed them using multiple comparisons (Bonferroni). In *Rhythm*, the mean score of Melody 3 is higher than that of Melody 1 ($p = 0.003$), and the mean score of Melody 3 is higher than that of Melody 2 ($p = 0.180$). In *Unity*, the mean score of Melody 3 is lower than that of Melody 1 ($p = 0.037$). In *Complexity*, the differences are not significant, but the mean score of Melody 3 is lower than that of Melody 1 ($p = 0.055$).

Amusement, *Positive*, *Negative*, and *Like* have no significant differences.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Experimental Purpose and Participants

Adjusting entropy leads to variations of appraisal about *Rhythm*, *Unity*, and *Complexity*. Therefore, the model of melodic rhythm is validated by our results. The differences between Melody 1 and Melody 2 are significant, but that between Melody 1 and Melody 3 and that be-

tween Melody 2 and Melody 3 do not tend to be significant. The reason may be that the listener could not sense small differences in entropies but could recognize big differences. A threshold of feeling could exist, and we will examine that possibility as a future task.

The differences in the appraisal of *Complexity* are significant. One reason might be that the experimental melodies were only based on values, and the pitches of notes were random; therefore, other properties of the melody might have created the feeling of *Complexity*. It is also possible that value and pitch are not independent, but interactive.

Amusement, *Positive*, *Negative*, and *Like* are not affected by adjusting the entropy, possibly because emotion and liking are elicited by deviation/realization of expectation.

In this paper, we proposed the model of rhythmic complexity, which could provide elements of deviation/realization. As a next step, we will implement these models.

6. CONCLUSIONS

We are developing a system that automatically creates melody based on deviation/realization of musical expectations. In this paper, we proposed the model of melodic rhythm based on entropy, and we verified that the model can provide musical complexity, which is one of the musical elements that elicit emotions.

7. REFERENCES

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